

TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT OF EMPLOYEES
IN INDIAN ORGANIZATIONS

Dr. Nilesh Thakre

Assistant Professor in Psychology

SNDT Women's University

Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

Abstract

Training and development of the employees improves productivity and organizational effectiveness. Training is an activity designed to equip personnel with needed knowledge, skill and attitude for the jobs, for which they are first recruited. This paper examine the usefulness of training for the workers as well as for the corporations, determines the major types of training and development programs, discusses the relationship between training and the overall organizational performance, and present guidelines for HR managers to design effective training and development programs.

Keywords: *Development, Evaluation of Training, Training, Training Methods, Training Need Identification.*

Introduction

Training is a process of assisting an employee for improving efficiency and effectiveness to achieve organizational goals and objectives. It is a learning process that involves the acquisition of knowledge, sharpening of skills, concepts, rules, or changing of attitudes and behaviors to enhance the performance of employees. Training and development are as important as well as organizational growth, because the organizational growth and profit are also dependent on the training.

Whereas, management development is all those activities and programme that have substantial influence in changing the capacity of the individual to perform his assigned job better and likely to increase his potential for future assignments. Thus, management development is the overall development of the competency of managerial personal in the light of the present requirement as well as the future requirement.

Objectives

- To elaborate the nature and importance of training and development
- To outline the training and development process in Indian organizations.
- To examine various training methods.
- To discuss the importance of evaluation of training
- To identify the various training g inputs required for different training programme.
- To delineate the different stages in a training and development programme and describe each step.

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Nature Of Training And Development

In simple terms, training and development refers to the imparting of specific skills, abilities and knowledge to an employee. It is an attempt to improve current or future employee performance by increasing an employee's ability to perform through learning, usually by changing the employee's attitude or increasing his or her skills and knowledge. The need for training & development is determined by the employee's performance deficiency, computed as follows:

Training & Development need = Standard performance – Actual performance.

Need for Training

After employees have been selected for various positions in an organization, training them for the specific tasks to which they have been assigned assumes great importance. It is true in many organizations that before an employee is fitted into a harmonious working relationship with other employees, he is given adequate training. Training is the act of increasing the knowledge and skills of an employee for performing a particular job. The major outcome of training is learning. A trainee learns new habits, refined skills and useful knowledge during the training that helps him improve performance. Training enables an employee to do his present job more efficiently and prepare himself for a higher-level job.

Training Need Identification (TNI) for an Organization

Training need identification is a tool utilized to identify what training courses or activities should be provided to employees to improve their productivity. Identification of training needs provides the basis for training activities. Identification of training needs is important from both the organizational point of view as well as from an individual's point of view. These objectives can be achieved only through harnessing the abilities of its people, releasing potential and maximizing opportunities for development. Through the effective training need identification people's aspirations can be fulfilled; the organization must provide effective and attractive learning resources and conditions. It is also important to see that there is a suitable match between achieving organizational goals and providing appropriate learning opportunities.

TRAINING METHODS

Training methods are usually classified by the location of instruction. On the job training is provided when the workers are taught relevant knowledge, skills and abilities at the actual workplace; off-the-job training, on the other hand, requires that trainees learn at a location other than the real work spot. Some of the widely used training methods are listed below.

On-The-Job Training Methods

The on-the-job methods are cost effective. Workers actually produce while they learn. Since immediate feedback is available, they motivate trainees to observe and learn the right way of doing things. Very few problems arise in the case of transfer of training because the employees learn in the actual work environment where the skills that are learnt are actually used. On-the-job methods may cause disruptions in production schedules. Experienced workers cannot use the facilities that are used in training. Poor learners may damage machinery and equipment. Finally, if the trainer does not possess teaching skills, there is very little benefit to the trainee. On-the-job training methods are as follows:

1. Job Instruction Training (JIT)

The JIT method (developed during World War II) is a four-step instructional process involving preparation, presentation, performance try out, and follow up. It is used primarily to teach workers how to do their current jobs. A trainer, supervisor or co-worker acts as the coach. The four steps followed in the JIT methods are:

1. The trainee receives an overview of the job, its purpose and its desired outcomes, with a clear focus on the relevance of training.
2. The trainer demonstrates the job in order to give the employee a model to copy. The trainer shows a right way to handle the job.
3. Next, the employee is permitted to copy the trainer's way. Demonstrations by the trainer and practice by the trainee are repeated until the trainee masters the right way to handle the job.
4. Finally, the employee does the job independently without supervision.

2. Coaching:

Coaching is a kind of daily training and feedback given to employees by immediate supervisors. It is an informal, unplanned training and development activity provided by

supervisors and peers. In coaching, the supervisor explains things and answers questions; throws light on why things are done the way they are; offers a model for trainees to copy; conducts lot of decision making meetings with trainees; procedures are agreed upon and the trainee is given enough authority to make decisions and even commit mistakes. Coaching can be a demanding job because the coach may not possess requisite skills to guide the learner in a systematic way. Sometimes, doing a full day's work may be more important than putting the learner on track.

3. Mentoring:

Mentoring is a relationship in which a senior manager in an organization assumes the responsibility for grooming a junior person. Technical, interpersonal and political skills are generally conveyed in such a relationship from the more experienced person. A mentor is a teacher, spouse, counsellor, developer of skills and intellect, host, guide, exemplar, and most importantly, supporter and facilitator in the realization of the vision the young person (protégé) has about the kind of life he wants as an adult.

The main objective is to help employees attain psychological maturity and effectiveness and get integrated with the organization. In a work situation, such mentoring can take place at both formal and informal levels, depending on the prevailing work culture and the commitment from the top management. Formal mentoring can be very fruitful, if management invests time and money in such relationship building exercises.

Mentoring in India is based on the time-honored guru-shishya relationship where the guru would do everything to develop the personality of the shishya, offering emotional support, and guidance. Companies like TISCO, Neyveli Lignite Corporation, Polaris, Coca-Cola India have used mentoring systems to good effect in recent times (Economic Times, 25 Oct., 2002).

4. Job Rotation:

Job rotation involves the movement of employee from one job to another. The purpose of job rotation is to provide trainees with a larger organizational perspective and a greater understanding of different functional areas as well as a better sense of their own career objectives

and interests. Apart from relieving boredom, job rotation allows trainees to build rapport with a wide range of individuals within the organization, facilitating future cooperation among departments. The cross-trained personnel offer a great amount of flexibility for organizations when transfers, promotions or replacements become inevitable.

5 Apprenticeship Training:

Most craft workers such as plumbers and carpenters are trained through formal apprenticeship programmes. Apprentices are trainees who spend a prescribed amount of time working with an experienced guide, coach or trainer. Assistantships and internships are similar to apprenticeships because they also demand high levels of participation from the trainee. An internship is a kind of on-the-job training that usually combines job training with classroom instruction in trade schools, colleges or universities.

6. Committee Assignments:

In this method, trainees are asked to solve an actual organizational problem. The trainees have to work together and offer solution to the problem. Assigning talented employees to important committees can give these employees a broadening experience and can help them to understand the personalities, issues and processes governing the organization. However, managers should very well understand that committee assignments could become notorious time wasting activities.

Off-The-Job Training Methods

In this method the trainee is separated from the job situation and his attention is focused upon learning the material related to his present and future job performance. Since the trainee is not distracted by job requirements, he can focus his entire concentration on learning the job rather than spending his time in performing it. There is an opportunity for freedom of expression for the trainees. Off-the-job training methods are as follows:

1. Vestibule training:

Vestibule training is the actual work conditions which are simulated in a classroom. Material, files and equipment that are used in actual job performance are used in the training. The duration of this training ranges from a few days to a few weeks. Theory can be related to practice in this method.

2. Role playing:

It is a method of human interaction that involves realistic behaviour in imaginary situations. This method of training involves action, doing and practice. The participants play the role of certain characters, such as the production manager, mechanical engineer, superintendents, maintenance engineers, quality control inspectors, foreman, workers and the like. This method is mostly used for developing interpersonal interactions and relations.

3. Lecture method:

The lecture is a traditional and direct method of instruction. The instructor organizes the material and gives it to a group of trainees in the form of a talk. To be effective, the lecture must motivate and create interest among the trainees. An advantage of lecture method is that it is direct and can be used for a large group of trainees. Thus, costs and time involved are reduced. The major limitation of the lecture method is that it does not provide for transfer of training effectively.

4. Conference/discussion approach:

In this method, the trainer delivers a lecture and involves the trainee in a discussion so that his doubts about the job get clarified. When big organisations use this method, the trainer uses audio-visual aids such as black boards, mockups and slides; in some cases the lectures are videotaped or audio taped. Even the trainee's presentation can be taped for self confrontation and self-assessment.

The conference is, thus, a group-centered approach where there is a clarification of ideas, communication of procedures and standards to the trainees. Those individuals who have a general educational background and whatever specific skills are required such as typing, shorthand, office equipment operation, filing, indexing, recording, etc. - may be provided with specific instructions to handle their respective jobs.

5. Programmed instruction:

This method has become popular in recent years. The subject matter to be learned is presented in a series of carefully planned sequential units. These units are arranged from simple to more complex levels of instruction. The trainee goes through these units by answering questions or filling the blanks. This method is, thus, expensive and time-consuming.

EVALUATION OF A TRAINING PROGRAMME

The specification of values forms a basis for evaluation. The basis of evaluation and the mode of collection of information necessary for evaluation should be determined at the planning stage. The process of training evaluation has been defined as any attempt to obtain information on the effects of training performance and to assess the value of training in the light of that information. Evaluation helps in controlling and correcting the training programme. There are five levels of evaluation of training can take place, viz., reactions, learning, job behaviour, organization and ultimate value.

1. Reactions:

Trainee's reactions to the overall usefulness of the training including the coverage of the topics, the method of presentation, the techniques used to clarify things, often throw light on the effectiveness of the programme. Potential questions to trainees might include: (i) What were your learning goals for the programme? (ii) Did you achieve them? (iii) Did you like this programme? (iv) Would you recommend it to others who have similar learning goals? (v) what suggestions do you have for improving the programme

2. Learning:

Training programme, trainer's ability and trainee's ability are evaluated on the basis of quantity of content learned and time in which it is learned and learner's ability to use or apply the content learned.

3. Job behaviour:

This evaluation includes the manner and extent to which the trainee has applied his learning to his job.

4. Organisation:

This evaluation measures the use of training, learning and change in the job behaviour of the department/organization in the form of increased productivity, quality, morale, sales turnover and the like.

5. Ultimate value:

It is the measurement of ultimate result of the contributions of the training programme to the company goals like survival, growth, profitability, etc. and to the individual goals like development of personality and social goals like maximizing social benefit.

Methods of Evaluation

Various methods can be used to collect data on the outcomes of training. Some of these are:

Questionnaires: Comprehensive questionnaires could be used to obtain opinions, reactions, and views of trainees.

Tests: Standard tests could be used to find out whether trainees have learnt anything during and after the training.

Interviews: Interviews could be conducted to find the usefulness of training offered to operatives.

Studies: Comprehensive studies could be carried out eliciting the opinions and judgments of trainers, superiors and peer groups about the training.

Human resource factors: Training can also be evaluated on the basis of employee satisfaction, which in turn can be examined on the basis of decrease in employee turnover, absenteeism, accidents, grievances, discharges, dismissals, etc.

Cost benefit analysis: The costs of training (cost of hiring trainers, tools to learn, training centre, wastage, production stoppage, opportunity cost of trainers and trainees) could be compared with its value in order to evaluate a training programme.

Feedback: After the evaluation, the situation should be examined to identify the probable causes for gaps in performance. The training evaluation information should be provided to the instructors, trainees and other parties concerned for control, correction and improvement of trainees' activities. The training evaluator should follow it up sincerely so as to ensure effective implementation of the feedback report at every stage.

Conclusion:

The training and development system should be meticulously planned and executed as per identified needs. It is essential to impart training on employee development at all levels so that the effectiveness of training could be increased by giving necessary support to one's subordinate and colleagues. The benefits accrued from training are not in proportion with the emphasis laid on it, training maximum employee's acts as a long-term investment and will essentially have a favourable outcome for organization.

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